

Special UAV requirements for Nordic conditions

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Summary

The Nordic Drone Initiative project defined the *urgent outdoor delivery* mission as a key use case for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in the Nordic countries. In this context, the successful deployment of drones in logistics missions requires an effort to quantify the special requirements for UAVs, with a focus on atmospheric icing and technologies for the power system based on fuel cells or batteries feeding the electric motors, versus internal combustion engines.

This report presents an overview on the aforementioned topics, produced as part of Nordic Drone initiative project funded by Nordic Innovation (2020 - 2022).

Atmospheric icing has been confirmed as a critical aspect to be addressed: when flying at 120m above ground level, the larger share of the territory in the Nordics already experiences icing 13 days per year, and the frequency of icing quickly increases in higher flight levels.

In low level flight operations with smaller drones, the risk of icing will be mitigated with use of weather data during mission planning, and icing awareness (real time readings from airborne sensors, & aircraft metrics) and protection of critical flight sensors.

Flying-wing UAV aircraft architecture seems well suited to minimize the effect of icing. In small helicopter-type UAVs (~200kg weight), the power required for ice prevention seems largely proportional to the power in helicopters certified for flight into known icing conditions. The protection of such UAVs against icing seems realizable with currently available technology, at a cost of a noticeable reduction in payload and flight range.

The power systems based on aviation fuel or fuel cell will likely be used for flight endurance over 30 minutes, whereas batteries continue to find its niche in the shorter missions. In both cases, low temperatures will limit operational capabilities.

Fuel cell power systems are getting closer to the performance of aviation fuel, with the promise to integrate with the future hydrogen economy. Improved design of fuel containers capable of storing liquid hydrogen will help closing the gap.

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1. Introduction

The deployment of drones in logistic missions across the Nordics will largely benefit from (i) the progress in drone power systems, capable of delivering extended operational range and higher payload; and (ii) the awareness about the harsh Nordic climate, and specially atmospheric icing and its effect in drone operations.

The analysis will focus on reference missions established in project Nordic Drone Initiative, in preceding work packages WP1 and WP2, which defined the *urgent outdoor delivery* as key value chain use cases. These missions are described in the next chapter.

In this context, this report presents an analysis on the following topics:

- Technology landscape in drone power systems, looking specifically at progress in fuel cell and battery technologies, critical to extend the operational envelope of drones, allowing them to fly longer with larger payloads.
- Investigating the occurrence of atmospheric icing conditions specific to drone flight in the Nordics, with a focus on specific use cases.
- Review of available technologies for aircraft ice prevention, looking specifically at the applicability to UAVs in the reference missions.

In this report, the term drone is used interchangeably with UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle), UAS (Unmanned Aircraft System) and RPAS (Remotely Piloted Aircraft System).

2. Reference UAV missions

The reference missions considered for the analysis correspond to the value chain use case “*outdoor urgent delivery*”. The key parameters are indicated in the table below:

value chain use case	reference case	reference payload mass [kg]	range, take-off to landing [km]	cruise altitude [ft]	mission profile	UAV architecture	UAV	maximum take-off weight [kg]	Reference system cost [kUSD]	Notes
Outdoor urgent delivery (spare part delivery)	Equinor, spare part delivery to Troll-A	34	80	5000 a.s.l.	vertical take-off, cruise, vertical landing	unmanned helicopter (single lifting rotor), breathing engine	Schiebel Camcopter s-100	200	2000	* System cost includes UAV plus ancillaries, base station and training * Reference payload allows 6h+ endurance at loiter speed. Maximum range 200km (both land and sea)
Outdoor urgent delivery (Health care: blood samples)	Oslo university hospital	3	2.5	350 a.g.l.	vertical take-off, cruise, vertical landing	unmanned quad-copter, battery	Globe UAV Aquila	9.3	60	System cost include drone and groundstation Reference payload 30min flight Maximum range 40km/60min Octocopter version 5 kg payload. 70min endurance
Outdoor urgent delivery (transport of biological samples)	Several flights in Norway	4	20	300 a.g.l	vertical take-off, cruise, vertical landing	Electric , 8 rotors paired in four arms	Sabrinus 4-20	20	-	Purpose-built for transportation of blood samples. Manufacturer Airlift solutions.

Table 1. Reference UAV missions considered in the analysis. References (1,2,3,4,5)

3. Icing climate

3.1 Cloud types relevant to in-flight icing

Supercooled water droplets present in clouds are responsible for in-cloud icing. The minimum temperature usually referenced for the existence of supercooled water droplets is -40°C . Generally the mean volumetric diameter (MVD) is less than 35 micron, but freezing rain may involve droplets as large as 1000microns (6).

Stratiform clouds are relevant when assessing UAV icing because they extend horizontally in the range 1 to 300 nautical miles, and result in icing conditions of long duration. The clouds are characterized by moderate Liquid Water Content (LWC) of maximum value $1.1\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (6). Ice accretion in these clouds is most frequently rime ice.

- High level stratiform clouds (above 6000m of altitude), which are composed mostly of ice crystals and do not cause airframe icing. Icing encounters above 7 km are rare.
- Middle level stratiform clouds (between 2km and 6km of altitude)
- low level stratiform clouds (below 2km altitude). Higher LWC and lower extension compared to middle level stratiform clouds.
- The overall average MVD for layer clouds is about 15 micron (7).

Cumuliform clouds extend in the range of 2 to 6 nautical miles, have short duration and occur in the range 1km – 2.4km AGL. The LWC is typically high up to $2.5\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ or even more in tropical regions. Typical MVD is in the range 9 to 50 microns (6) with an overall average about 19 micron (7). Ice accretion in this case is either glace or mixed glace ice – rime ice (6).

Icing events in cumuliform clouds tend to be short , but can be about two to three times as severe as events in stratiform clouds due to the high liquid water content (8).

3.2 Freezing rain

The mechanism of freezing rain occurs when thermal inversion in the atmosphere causes precipitation to freeze, resulting in supercooled large droplets of 1000 microns which froze upon impact, forming glace ice (8). Typical LWC in freezing rain events is $0.15\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Normally freezing rain occurs in the altitude range 0 – 5000 ft (0 – 1 500m). Pilots are cautioned to avoid flying in freezing rain conditions, which is extremely dangerous because of rapid ice accretion (6).

3.3 Atmospheric icing at different levels in the nordics.

Atmospheric icing examination is based on VTT WICEAtlas (9) model. WiceAtlas is created using meteorological data from land-based weather stations (10). The icing model is based on more than 20 years of measurement and observation data and is normally used to evaluate icing conditions relevant to wind turbines and other tall structures.

The icing conditions in the WiceAtlas database are defined as icing frequency [% of time]. WiceAtlas only covers in-cloud icing and the icing frequency represents meteorological, active icing conditions i.e. the fraction of the time when there is a chance of ice accretion on surfaces.

The observation time series used in building the WiceAtlas database was from 1979 to 2017. As every observation station has different data availability and quality the following measures were used to select the stations used to build the global map:

- at least 20 years of data per station (total, not continuous), and
- at least 70 % of data availability per station.

This selection criteria left approximately 4500 observation stations globally to be used to build the global icing map. Because temperature at the weather stations is measured at the ground level, additional temperature data from MERRA2 reanalysis data (11) is used to achieve a better estimate of temperature at higher elevations.

The icing model is based on cloud base height measurements, and the goal was to capture in-cloud icing only. Used icing criterion is that cloud base height is below a set level and temperature is below zero. The method used is based on work done in WECO (12) and New Icetools (13) projects and on later work by Lasse Makkonen at VTT (14).

Figure 1: WiceAtlas interpolation principle

A cumulative vertical icing profile is built using temperature and cloud base height measurements for every weather station. Then a linear fit was applied to this profile to get a model for the vertical icing profile. The stations-specific icing profile was then combined with elevation data to estimate icing on a given location (see Figure 1). The linear vertical icing profile was then interpolated between the 10 closest station using inverse distance weighting to get an icing profile for any given location (15).

The method used to estimate meteorological icing produces an on-off criteria for icing, but does not yield an estimate for icing intensity. Ultimately icing intensity depends on wind speed and liquid water content of the air during an icing event as well as shape of the object that is collecting ice. The final map that is produced is calibrated against publically available icing analysis from Sweden and Canada to produce a best possible estimate for the wind power use case (16,17).

The goal of the calibration was to correctly match the estimated production losses of wind farms to the meteorological icing of IEA ice classification (18). For the wind power use case WIceAtlas has been found to give a relatively good estimate of the long-term icing frequency (19,20,21,22).

3.4 Key atmospheric icing metrics in the nordics

Using the vertical icing profiles stored in the WIceAtlas database we can then interpolate a map of icing time in the Nordics at different heights *above ground level*. These maps are illustrated in the next pages at relevant heights. The maps represent the icing frequency in the WIceAtlas database and show the % of time of meteorological icing in the area.

It is good to note that all the validations against measurements have been done at heights below 200m above ground level. The blank areas in the map are areas where the relative differences in elevation are too large (> 500 m difference in elevation between observation and map location).

Please note that the color scale in the maps is different at different heights. Icing frequency increases as height increases.

Some conclusions can be drawn simply from looking at the maps:

- Significant change in icing frequency at lower end (90m – 120m – 150m).
- Flying at 120m agl, most of the map shows icing time below 3.6% of the time (approximately 13 icing days per year). This means that RPAS/drone operation in low level flight has a relatively minor icing impact in most of the areas.
- Icing frequency increases significantly above 500 m.

The frequency of icing from WIceAtlas is comparable to the values presented in (23,24).

Figure 2: Atmospheric icing time (% of year) at 90m, 120m and 150m above ground level

Figure 3: Atmospheric icing time (% of year) at 200m, 250m and 300m above ground level

Figure 4: Atmospheric icing time (% of year) at 500m, 1000m and 1500m above ground level

Figure 5: Atmospheric icing time (% of year) at 2000m above ground level

4. Sizing of full ice protection system in rotorcraft

4.1 Case of conventional helicopter

The ice protection system in conventional rotorcraft may be classified (25,26) as:

- Limited Ice Protection System (LIPS), which “permits flight within a known and defined envelope of icing conditions, provided that the capability to descend to a known band of positive temperature is available through the intended route”. This basic level of protection includes ice detectors, super-cooled large droplet (SLD) marker, ice accretion meter and heated windshield, together with the standard engine air intake heating system.
- Full Ice Protection System (FIPS), which allows the rotorcraft to operate in known icing conditions. This system enhances the LIPS by incorporating rotorblade ice protection in the the main and tail rotors, ice detectors, automatic activation system and manual back-up, engine intake protection grid, and heated windshield.

The helicopter AgustaWestland AW139 uses a FIPS with heating mats installed in the rotors (27) and fitting two alternators of 25kVA and 45kVA rated power (28) for an approximated 70kW maximum heating power to the rotors. Electrical power to the blades is controlled by control box and distributed through distribution boxes and slip rings. Atmospheric information is provided by outside ambient temperature and ice detectors (liquid water content) (29).

Considering for the AW139 aircraft a Maximum Continuous Power of 1492 kW (30). The rated power of the FIPS represents 4.7% of the Maximum Continuous Power.

4.2 Scaling law for rotor ice protection

In order to read-across the power demand required for thermal rotor ice prevention between two different rotorcraft configurations, an approximate expression is derived on the following assumptions:

- Heat transfer driven by turbulent flat plate convection (31) between leading edge of blade at temperature T_s and surrounding air at temperature T_∞ . The expression used for the average Nusselt number Nu as a function of Reynolds and Prandtl numbers is $Nu = 0.037 * Re^{4/5} * Pr^{1/3}$.
- Local air speed in the blade given only by the blade rotation term ($\Omega \cdot r$), discarding forward flight contribution.
- Heated area covers a fraction ξ of the aircraft chord c , so that the heated area per unit span is $2 \cdot \xi \cdot c$ (both pressure side and suction side).

In these conditions, the combined heating power [Watts] required by all the rotors is given by the following expression:

$$P_{rotors} = \underbrace{0.041 \Omega^{4/5} N_b N_r (c \xi)^{4/5} (R_1^{9/5} - R_0^{9/5})}_{\text{aircraft design}} \underbrace{k^{2/3} \mu^{-7/15} c_p^{1/3} \rho_\infty^{4/5} (T_s - T_\infty)}_{\text{ambient conditions}} \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where all units are in the International System of Units, and k is the air conductivity [W/m-K], μ the air viscosity [Pa.s], cp the air specific heat capacity [J/kg-K], ρ the air density [kg/m³], N_b the number of blades per rotor, N_r the number of rotors; and R_0 , R_1 respectively the inboard and outboard radius of the heated area.

The expression above shows the dependency of rotor heating power on the reference ambient conditions as well as on the aircraft design parameters.

Application of Equation 1 to the aforementioned case of the helicopter AgustaWestland AW139 yields the following estimated heating power requirement for the main rotor:

Flight altitude [ft]	ISA ΔT	Outside Ambient Temperature [deg C]	T_s [degC]	Ω [rpm]	R_1 [m]	R_0 [m]	c [m]	N_b	N_r	ξ heated fraction of chord [-]	P rotors [kW] (equation 1)
5000	-25	-20	2	300	6.9	0	0.5	5	1	0.25	67.26
10000	-25	-30	2	300	6.9	0	0.5	5	1	0.25	85.78

Table 2. Estimation of main rotor ice protection in case of helicopter AW139 using equation 1

The range of values obtained are in line with the rated power of 70kW used by the FIPS system. The same formula will be used in the next chapter to estimate the heating requirement for UAVs in the reference missions.

4.3 Estimated power demand and energy required for rotor ice protection:

The same Equation 1 is applied to two of the reference missions, in order to estimate the power required for rotor ice protection. For the UAV Schiebel Camcopter 100, the rotor speed Ω , rotor tip radius R_1 and engine rated power were taken from references (32,33), and other magnitudes were estimated from public images. Take-off weight for Sabrinus 4-20 UAV was provided by UAS Norway, and other values were estimated.

The analysis shows that power requirement to protect these UAVs against icing in their reference missions would require approximately 6% of their rated power in case of the *spare part delivery mission*, a value slightly higher but similar to the requirement for a medium sized helicopter such as the AW139 (4.7%).

The smaller Sabrinus 4-20, flying at 300ft above ground level would require approximately 3% of its rated power to protect its rotors.

Based on this analysis, it seems that rotorcraft UAV in these two missions can be reasonably protected against icing similarly as medium sized helicopters certified to fly into known icing conditions (for example AW139), with a noticeable effect in the mission parameters (payload or range).

Reference mission	Flight altitude [ft]	ISA ΔT	Outside Ambient Temperature [deg C]	T_s [degC]	Ω [rpm]	R1 [m]	R0 [m]	chord [m]	Nb	Nr	ξ heated fraction of chord [-]	P rotors [kW] (equation 1)	Rated power [kW] (engine or generator)	P rotor heating / P rated [%]
Spare part delivery (Equinor, Schiebel)	5000ft a. s. l.	-25	-20	2	1178	1.70	0	0.14	2	1	0.25	2.39	41	6%
Transport of biological samples (Sabrinus)	300ft a. g. l.	-25	-11	2	9000	0.16	0	0.02	2	8	0.25	0.14	4.7	3%

Table 3. Estimation of power requirement for rotor ice protection in two reference missions

4.4 Scaling law for fixed-wing ice protection

A scaling law for thermal ice protection in fixed-wing aircraft can be obtained similarly as for the rotorcraft case (also here the International System of Units is used in formulas).

In this case, the power required for ice prevention in the wing or the tail control surfaces/empennage is given by the formula below, where V_∞ is the air speed and A_R is the wing aspect ratio (ratio between the wing surface and the mean aerodynamic chord).

$$P_{wing} = \underbrace{0.074 V_\infty^{4/5} A_R c (c \xi)^{4/5}}_{\text{aircraft design}} \underbrace{k^{2/3} \mu^{-7/15} c_p^{1/3} \rho_\infty^{4/5} (T_s - T_\infty)}_{\text{ambient conditions}} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The expression above can be rearranged to present the dependency on wing aspect ratio and the wing surface S_{wing} :

$$P_{wing} = 0.074 A_R^{1/10} \xi^{4/5} S_{wing}^{9/10} V_\infty^{4/5} k^{2/3} \mu^{-7/15} c_p^{1/3} \rho_\infty^{4/5} (T_s - T_\infty) \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

From the equation above it can be seen that fixed wing aircraft with low aspect ratio have lower power demand for the same wing surface. This is a result of smaller leading edge area exposed to droplet impingement.

Another qualitative consideration is that having no empennage is an advantage from the perspective of icing protection.

Considering fixed wing aircraft, flying wings with low wing aspect ratio seem best suited to minimize heating power consumption for ice prevention.

This requirement is conflicting with the endurance requirement, which favours wings with high aspect ratio. The combined requirements of high endurance and protection against icing may result in very high power requirements for thermal ice protection.

5. Technology landscape : methods for icing protection

Protection of conventional aircraft against atmospheric icing is regarded a consolidated technology while there is still potential for optimization. When flight into known icing conditions becomes mission critical, there are proven technologies to enable aircraft to operate safely. This chapter reviews the available technologies, with a commentary on their applicability to UAVs such as those presented in the reference missions.

5.1 Technologies for icing protection, and applicability to reference missions

5.1.1 Pneumatic boot

The pneumatic boot has been used since their invention by Goodrich company in 1930's and continue to be a proven and well-accepted technology today for use in small and medium size aircraft (34). It is essentially an inflatable insert bonded to the wing leading edge, which breaks the ice periodically after it forms. Their advantages are light weight, low power demand, and low operation cost.

The system concept for rubber boot deicing has remain largely unchanged. An alternative to neoprene material, namely Estane is being offered by Collings Aerospace Goodrich Deicing with higher durability and improved ice shedding (35).

Typical power rating and weight for a single engine general aviation fixed wing aircraft Bonanza is 775W and 24kg (36). Bonanza has maximum take-off weight (MTOW) 1656kg , rated engine power 224kW. Power demand of boots icing protection for wings is 0.4% of aircraft rated power, and the system mass represents 1.5% of MTOW.

Indicative boot system replacement costs for a single engine aircraft such as the Bonanza were 11kUSD as of 2012 (37). Typical longevity between 3-4 years in commuter airliners, and 5-10 years with less demanding use (36,37). An indicative price for a Bonanza was 700kUSD (2006).

Thickness of rubber boot is 2.2mm thick (34,38) including all layers between the protected surface and the ice. The rubber boot can be embedded in the wing structure, in a recessed leading edge (38), in order to to prevent steps affecting the aerodynamics.

Pneumatic boots are manufactured for aerodynamic elements as small as the tail of general aviation aircraft. For example Collings Aerospace manufactures a boot for the horizontal stabilizer of the Pilatus PC-12, with chord approximately 0.75m.

Integration in significantly smaller wings presents challenges due to miniaturization. A minimum skin thickness is required in order to bear the inflation pressure load and the shear stress in the skin in contact with the ice. A typical general aviation airfoil such as NACA2412 has a leading edge radius 1.6% of the chord. A leading edge radius of 4.4mm (twice the rubber boot thickness of 2.2mm) would resulting in a typical wing chord of 0.275m.

Arguably, the pneumatic boot system would not be suitable for the aircraft in the reference missions, because of the complexity required to integrate a rotary wing with a pressurized air system , as well as the very small chord dimension in the rotor.

However, the pneumatic boot system seems suitable for medium altitude medium endurance UAV such as the Tekever AR5, with wing and tail chords of 0.4 - 0.5m and take-off weight of 180 kg (39).

5.1.2 Fluid

The “weeping wing” solution (sometimes called TKS, initials of consortium companies who developed the concept in the 1940s) has been used to upgrade the MQ-1 Predator UAV, following loss of an aircraft due to icing in 1999 (23) . The aircraft system operational in 2005 relied on glycol-weeping “wet wings”.

Predator weeping wing, featured porous laser drilled titanium panels to distribute glycol-based fluid to wing and stabilizers (40). Typically the outer panel is titanium sheet 0.7-0.9mm thick, with 0.0025 inch diameter holes (800/sq inch). The system can be integrated as part of wing design or added to the leading edge as a retrofit. The mono-ethylene glycol mixes with in-air moisture to reduce the freezing point to -76F/-60C (35).

In a typical General Aviation installation such as the Bonanza, the full system which protects the wing, wind screen and propeller require a rated power of 42W, and an overall weight of 50kg, including 18kg hardware and 32kg liquid for 2.5hour operation. Fluid is delivered to the propeller via a slinger ring, which rotates with the propeller and collects the fluid to deliver it to the blade root through a discharge pipe.

The values for a MQ-1 Predator (MTOW = 1020kg) would be smaller compared to the Bonanza (MTOW = 1656kg).

The TKS system is marketed as retrofit for a range of aircraft, including small general aviation aircraft such as the Cessna 210, with average aircraft retail price of 230kUSD (41).

Compared to the pneumatic boot, the TKS system has lower power demand, arguably better aerodynamics, and longer durability. It seems more suitable for smaller wings compared to the pneumatic boot.

The main disadvantages are the weight and the environmental impact of chemical substances (42), due to the release of chemicals during flight.

5.1.3 Electro-Thermal

Electrothermal ice prevention use Joule heating applied to aerodynamic surfaces exposed to impinging droplets. Two operation modes are typically considered:

- *anti-icing*, where the heating power is enough to keep the protected surface ice-free, and
- *de-icing*, where an operation cycle is defined that allows ice growth and applies periodic heat to melt ice in the interface with the leading edge and force ice shedding.

Recent research (43) comparing performance of both approaches in UAV wing application estimate that conventional antiicing specific heating demand ranges 1.5 - 7.5kW/m² at 25m/s flight speed, liquid water content of 0.44g/m³, and air temperatures between -2C and -10C. De-icing in the same conditions has a power demand between 0.2kW/m² and 2.5kW/m².

The range 1 – 2kW/m² has been also reported as representative of cyclic de-icing in electrothermal medium altitude long endurance (MALE) fixed wing UAV applications. The range for anti-icing in this case has been estimated as 10-20kW/m² (23).

For comparison, the estimated specific heating power demand in the AgustaWestland AW139 helicopter was around 8kW/m². The high aerodynamic speed of rotor blades (217m/s for the AW139) increases heat transfer and specific heating power compared to fixed wing aircraft.

Considering the fixed-wing drone/UAS Tekever AR5, an airplane with MTOW of 180kg, the estimated wing leading edge area to be protected is 2.61m². In this case the range 0.2 - 2.5 kW/m² results in an indicative heating demand of 0.5 – 6.5kW. The equation 2 estimates 7.1kW for the combination of wing and empennage (propellers excluded).

The estimate is higher than the Power demand of 2.4kW for the Schiebel Camcopter S-100 (MTOW 200kg), which requires much smaller leading edge area to be protected, namely 0.25m².

The Tekever AR5 has a high aspect ratio ~13 which results in a considerable wing section to be protected. The high aspect ratio results in a good endurance of 20 hours, compared to the 6-10 hour endurance for the S-100.

From these examples it seems that both fixed wing and rotary wing aircraft of comparable take-off weight would require a broadly similar amount of heating for ice prevention.

Qualitatively it also seems reasonable to reduce empennage area to prevent ice accretion. This reasoning leads to a flying wing with low aspect ratio and low cruise flight speed as a desirable configuration from icing point of view.

5.1.4 Electro-Mechanical

The electro-mechanical de-icing systems rely on the application of an impulsive force by means of electric actuators which flex the leading edge surface and break the ice.

For example the Sonic Pulse Electro-Impulse De-Icing (SPEED) developed by Innovative dynamics Inc. (IDI) produces a single current pulse in a coil, generating an electromagnetic force which deflects the outer surface. This system was reported to shed ice as thin as 1.27mm, offering lightweight and low-power protection (40).

Similarly, the Electro-Mechanical Expulsion Deicing System (EMEDS) from Cox & Company (44) is able to remove an ice layer of same thickness, and requires power of 300W to deice a wing span of 12.8m.

The Electro-Expulsive De-Icing System (EEDS) is used by UK aircraft Thales Watchkeeper WK450 Mk 1 based on Elbit's Hermes 450 with take-off weight 500kg. Protection covers wing and V-tail. Each EEDS is formed by an actuator placed between layers of carbon fibre. When a large electric current is fed to the actuator, the electromagnetic force deforms the leading edge causing ice removal.

The aircraft reference icing conditions (continuous maximum icing conditions) are liquid water content between 0.2 – 0.8g/m³, and droplet sizes of 15-40micron over a 17.4nm encounter (45,46).

Furthermore, the use of small amplitude vibration in the leading edge by means of piezoelectric actuators is an active field of research (47) with a potential to further reduce the energy consumption of ice prevention systems.

5.1.5 Hybrid Electro-Thermal + Electro-Mechanical

The latest advancements in active ice protection aim to combine electro-thermal and electro-mechanical principles to deliver the same effectiveness of thermal systems at a fraction of the power demand.

The Thermo-Mechanical Expulsion Deicing System (TMEDS) melts a thin layer of ice at the interface between ice and leading edge, and removes it with EMEDS actuators (44). The power demand is 2.3kW for a wing span of 12.8m.

Considering for example a Hawker 400 light jet (13m wing span), protecting 20% of the chord with 2.3kW would result in a specific power demand of 0.26 kW/m².

The TMEDS system is fitted in the UAV Northrop Grumman MQ-4C Triton (MTOW 14628 kg).

Recently the SEaSIDE project (2017-2021) has engaged in the development of a hybrid ice protection system combining thermal and electro-expulsive methods (48). The prototype has targeted a continuous power demand of 0.6kW/m of span for the Piaggio P 180 aircraft.

The Piaggio P 180 Avanti II has MTOW 5239kg, wing span 13.84m and wing area 16m², so the target power to protect the wing would be 8.3kW (0.6kW/m of span).

The prototype protects approximately 20% of the wing chord against icing, and the estimated specific power demand for the ice protection system is 1.3kW/m².

5.1.6 Engine bleed air

Hot-air thermal deicing uses air bled from the engine to feed a chamber inside the leading edge of the wing. A so-called "piccolo" tube is routed through a hollow chamber inside the leading edge of the wing, which has a plurality of orifices releasing hot air jets pointed towards the inner surface of the leading edge. Heat is carried to the external part of the leading edge, maintaining a temperature above freezing in the outer surface of the leading edge, and effectively preventing ice formation.

The system may be fitted to fixed wing aircraft fitted with breathing engine. In these applications it is effective but it may affect significantly the performance of the aircraft (40).

Furthermore, implementation in small UAV would require miniature air circuits: a typical piccolo tube radius is in the order of the wing leading edge radius. In case of general aviation airfoil NACA 2412, the leading edge radius is 1.6% of the wing chord.

	Ice prevention concept					
Design criteria	Pneumatic Boot	Fluid (TKS type)	Electro-Thermal	Electro-Mechanical (electro-expulsive)	Hybrid Electro-Thermal + Electro-Mechanical	engine bleed air
Erosion surface life	Months - 5 years (elastomer)	Life of aircraft (titanium)	Life of aircraft (metal/composite)	Life of aircraft (metal/composite)	Life of aircraft (metal/composite)	Life of aircraft (metal)
aircraft performance effect (drag increase or reduced thrust)	Measurable increase	Minimal increase	No increase	No increase	No increase	Substantial increase due to compressor air bleed
Deicing performance	ice thicker than 6mm typically	Anti-ice system. Requires activation prior to icing event in order to be effective	Runback ice accumulates downstream of leading edge.	Deicing, as low as 1.3mm no upper limit	As low as frost, no upper limit	As low as frost , no upper limit
Weight	Comparable to baseline	Heavier due to fluid reservoir	Comparable to baseline	Baseline	slightly greater than baseline	Comparable to baseline
Cost	Comparable to baseline	Costlier due to fluid usage	Comparable to baseline	Baseline	greater than baseline	costlier due to integration with propulsion system
Power demand, overall system [Watts], 12.8m wing span	1000W	42W	2000 to >20000W	300W	2300W	Higher than electrothermal
specific power demand [kW/m ²] (per unit protected wet area)	-	-	~ 0.2-2.5kW/m ² (deicing) ~ 1.5-7.5kW/m ² (antiicing)	-	~ 0.26 kW/m ² (deicing) ~1.3kW/m ² (antiicing)	-
Environmental aspects	none	release of chemicals during flight	none	none	none	none
Other advantages and disadvantages affecting suitability for UAV/RPAS	*aircraft performance degradation * requires frequent inspection * Challenging for chord < 0.3m due to miniaturization challenges	* proven solution for MTOW ~1700kg (MQ-1 Predator) * provides moderate icing protection * minor compromise to mission performance due to the extremely low power demand	* simplicity (no moving parts) * arguably a fine compromise for small UAVs in moderate icing, provided that heat delivery cycle is optimized	* proven solution for MTOW ~500kg (Hermes 450) * low power consumption	* proven solution for MTOW ~ 15000kg (MQ-4C Triton) *best-in-class deicing performance * costly and heavy	* aircraft performance effect * high power demand

Table 4. Design criteria of active ice prevention systems and suitability to UAV / RPAS (adapted from 44, 49).

5.1.7 Passive ice prevention

Passive ice prevention involves the creation of a icephobic surface, namely having a combination of properties resulting in very low ice accumulation in the aerodynamic surfaces. This is due to some of the effects listed below (51):

- prevent freezing of water condensating in the surface (frost),
- prevent freezing of incoming water,
- having very low adhesion force to ice (e.g. shear strength below 500kPa).

In the context of aerospace applications in UAVs, a potential icephobic surface needs to withstand also rain erosion wear, environmental degradation due to UV, thermal cycles, and saline environment (offshore applications); and also be easily applicable and serviceable.

Significant research has explored the effect of surface texture at micro and nanoscale in icephobicity, achieving good icephobic performance in laboratory. However, the solutions explored so far cannot withstand neither erosion nor repeated de-icing cycles. This is because texturing of the exposed aerodynamic surface has so far resulted in a surface susceptible of damage by erosion from impinging droplets and particles during flight. Also mechanical damage during icing-deicing cycles affects surface topology.

Polysiloxane (silicone based polymers): have good ice adhesion reduction factor but needs a primer for non-silica substrates (49). Generally they are considered as having low erosion resistance to dust, salt and ice particles, however some polysiloxanes are reported as erosion resistant, notably Nusil R-2180 (53).

Fluorinated polymeric coatings can provide icephobic properties by reducing the surface energy (50), but low durability limits practical aerospace applications (49).

Performance of existing products suggests (49) that surface properties alone cannot provide the ice prevention function, however coatings may promote water runback. For this purpose, hydrophobicity and low surface roughness are desirable characteristics.

5.1.8 Combined active and passive ice prevention

Ice prevention combining active and passive principles (49,52) involves an active ice prevention method supplemented with an ice phobic coating to reduce runback icing from melted water, and promote ice shedding. High conductivity coating may be use to enhance heat transfer from heating elements to the ice.

In this context, high elastic modulus in the surface material has been proven beneficial to attain high tensile and shear stress in the interface between wing and ice, adding to the effectiveness of active vibration. These stiffer coatings should be used to promote mechanical shedding of ice (53). Conversely, a soft coating such as Nusil R-2180 will interfere with the operation of electromechanical ice prevention, reducing the mechanical load in the interface, which drives ice shedding.

5.1.9 Carburetor icing

Carburetor icing is a well known phenomena affecting aircraft powered by internal combustion engines. Air temperature in the carburetor drops as a result of both Ventury effect and fuel evaporative cooling. This results in formation of frost at ambient temperatures above freezing, provided that relative humidity is sufficiently high.

Generally (54), carburetor ice will form in air temperatures between 0 deg C and +10 deg C with relative humidity above 50%. If visible moisture is present, it will form between -9 deg C and 0 deg C. Carburetor air temperature (CAT) gauge is recommended in combination with carburetor heating.

Carburator icing in UAV flights has been reported (55) in relatively mild conditions: -1.8degC and +57% relative humidity, +3degC and 87% relative humidity). Ice accretion was observed in drone control rod in swash plate, air intake, and in the internal duct leading to the carburetor. Ice was seen in a post-flight inspection of the drone.

5.1.10 Air systems icing

Ice may accumulate in exposed air intakes, throttle valves, heat valves etc.

In the aircraft industry air intakes are typically protected by engine bleed air, or pneumatic boots or electrothermal heating mats (49). Ice protection in UAVs is simpler when no air system is present (e.g. no engine air intake or oil cooling intake). This consideration favours electric engines and fuel cells with regards to the icing requirement.

Figure 6: Air intake icing in a drone powered by combustion engine. Image courtesy of CybAero AB (55)

5.1.11 Sensor icing

Aircraft flight sensors such as pitot-static probes are typically protected with electrical heaters. UAVs capable of flying with fewer and more protected sensors will be less exposed to icing.

6. Technology landscape : Batteries and hydrogen fuel cells

The power systems of UAVs are based on three technologies: internal combustion engines (ICE), electric motors with batteries and electric motors with fuel cells. The drones powered by ICE can currently provide the best performance in terms of operational range and payload. However, the ICE typically run on fossil fuels, which are not a sustainable solution and does not fit with international targets of net-zero greenhouse gas emissions (56,57,58). The energy for electric motors can be produced with renewable energy and stored in batteries or in the form of hydrogen. Therefore, the focus here is in the battery and hydrogen-powered drones. The petrol-powered ICE offers a good benchmark for the two.

Petrol has energy density of 12 kWh/kg (43.2 MJ/kg) and volumetric energy density of 8.8 kWh/l (32.7 MJ/l) (59). ICEs running on petrol have typically thermal efficiency of 30 %, but with recent advancements, higher efficiencies have been reached (60). Still, the drive cycle of the engine affects substantially to the total actual efficiency, which is typically smaller than the efficiency at optimal rotational speed. The size of the engine has also big impact on the efficiency. For example for engines smaller than 10 cubic centimetre, the efficiency falls below 10 % and in general, smaller engines have lower efficiencies (61).

Hydrogen has energy density of 33.3 kWh/kg (120 MJ/kg) and the volumetric energy density depends on the form of storage; compressed hydrogen at 700 bar has 1.5 kWh/l (5.6 MJ/l) (62) and liquid hydrogen 2.4 kWh/l (8.5 MJ/l) (59). Hydrogen thus contains almost three times the energy of petrol of the same mass, but in a bigger volume. However, the mass of the gas container reduces the advantage of hydrogen, as the currently available high pressure gas cylinders weight multiple times the mass of hydrogen they can store. For example HES Energy systems' A series 12 litre hydrogen cylinder has empty weight of 3.85 kg and can store 303 g of hydrogen at 350 bar, which translates to energy density of 1.1 kWh/kg (63,64). BMW demonstrated in 2011 storage for cryo-compressed hydrogen operating below 350-bar pressure. It had hydrogen capacity of 7.8 kg and total weight of 145 kg, resulting in thermal energy density of 1.8 kWh/kg (65). Toyota has extended the weight percent of a hydrogen container to 5.7 % corresponding to about 1.9 kWh/kg energy content in Mirai fuel cell vehicle with 700-bar compressed hydrogen in composite cylinders (66). Using lighter gas cylinder materials or liquid hydrogen storage solutions lead to higher energy densities. The thermal efficiency of fuel cells are typically about 54 %.

The state of the art Li-ion battery systems can store 0.250 kWh/kg, about 0.650 kWh/l, and electric motor system can use the energy with about 90 % efficiency (67,68). In a real life example, the Tesla Model S P85 electric car, the lithium polymer (LiPo) battery system has energy density of 0.157 kWh/kg and 0.275 kWh/l (69). Another form of Li-ion battery is the so-called lithium high voltage (LiHV) battery, which has a higher voltage than the LiPo battery. From possible future battery technologies, metal-air batteries are one of the most promising (70). For this battery type, the technology is most advanced with Zn-air batteries, which have theoretical energy density of 1.35 kWh/kg (71), but at the moment their life-cycle is limited to a couple of recharges (72). The batteries are currently having the lowest energy density of the three compared technologies, but they are easily accessible and there are already great number of battery-powered UAS solutions available.

There are three example user cases, for which we map most suitable options. Because the size of the UAS has a big impact on the system performance, it is worthwhile to compare different scale UAS cases separately with the three power systems. In addition, operability of the power system options in cold climate is reviewed.

6.1 Lightweight drones

Two of the selected user cases are in medical sector transporting biological samples in urban areas between medical facilities. The drone required should have capability of carrying a payload of at least 3 kg. The required operating ranges are 2.5 km and 20 km in the two cases, but the frequency of the transportation need is not defined. The drones taken in to the comparison and their specifications are listed in Table 4.

Only multirotor drones or helicopters without fixed wing were taken into the comparison, as these systems are in general more user friendly and easier to operate than the fixed wing systems. The maximum take-off weights (MTOW) of the drones were between 9.3 kg and 27 kg. The control techniques in communication between the drone and the controller are not discussed, as these do not depend on the used power system, but on the choice of the drone manufacturer and the end user.

In this size of drones, petrol engines are typically not used directly to power the rotors of a drone as small ICEs have low power-to-mass ratio, typically between 1 – 2 kW/kg, while electric engines have power-to-mass ratio above 4 kW/kg (61,73). In addition, the operation and maintenance of multiple small ICEs is demanding. Therefore, in small-scale drones petrol engines are used in hybrid power mode together with electric engines. In the hybrid system, a single ICE runs to convert petrol energy into electricity to power electric engines spinning the rotors. A battery can be used to equalise fluctuations in power consumption in different stages of flight.

Three examples of the petrol-hybrid system quadcopters are Avartek Boxer hybrid drone, Quaternium Hybrix 2.1 and Perimeter 8 from Skyfront (74,75,76). Avartek Boxer can in its heavier configuration of 27 kg with additional fuel, fly with 2 kg payload for 4 hours and 36 minutes. With 5 kg payload the flight time is still 2 hours. The Avartek Boxer has been already tested in winter conditions in surveying icebreaker leads in Northern Sweden, so its cold performance can be expected to be sufficient in most applications.

The Quaternium Hybrix 2.1 has empty weight of 13 kg and can carry even 10 kg payload with MTOW of 25 kg. The announced maximum flight time is 4 hours and with the maximum payload it is reduced to 2 hours. The minimum operational temperature given for the Hybrix 2.1 is -10 °C. In 2020, the Hybrix 2.1 made a petrol hybrid-drone world record of 10 hours and 14 minutes continuous flight (77). The record was made with enhanced fuel-injection system and a 16-litre fuel tank.

However, in 2021, the hexacopter Perimeter 8 from Skyfront, made a new record of 13 hours and 4 minutes continuous flight (76). Its endurance with payload is similar to Hybrix 2.1 and Boxer: 2 hours with 5 kg payload and 3 hours with 4 kg payload (78). The minimum expected operational temperature for Perimeter 8 is the same -10 °C as for the Hybrix 2.1, however the manufacturer offers a customised version, which can operate even in -30 °C. The petrol engine hybrid drones are thus well established and the technology is readily available for even longer flight missions.

The battery-powered drones can be also easily found in the market for this scale of drones. They are easy to operate and maintain, but they are typically limited by short flight endurance of about 30 minutes. However, there are some options that can fly longer. A good example is G3 Tactical Drone from Height Technologies. G3 Tactical drone is a quadcopter and can carry payload of 3 kg with maximum flight time of 50 minutes and with 0.3 kg payload it can stay airborne for 90 minutes. The MTOW is 11 kg, so the drone is relatively lightweight. The lowest operating temperature for G3 Tactical drone is -10 °C, close to some of the petrol-hybrid drones, but one can expect cold temperatures to reduce the flight endurance of the battery-powered drone to some extent.

Drones		Avartek Boxer	Quaternium Hybrix 2.1	Perimeter 8	G3 Tactical Drone	Sabrinus 4-20	GUAV8L Ceptor	GUAV4L Aquila	Skylle 1550	Hydrone 1550	Hydrone 1800	Hycoper	DZ15 (Doosan)
power system		petrol hybrid	petrol hybrid	petrol hybrid	LiPo battery	battery	LiPo battery	LiPo battery	LiHV battery	fuel cell hybrid	fuel cell hybrid	fuel cell hybrid	fuel cell hybrid
Maximum take-off weight MTOW[kg]		27	25	23	11	20	14.6	9.3	21 - 23	22		16.5	20
Operating empty weight [kg]		16.5	13		8 (with batteries)		10.6 (with batteries)	6.3 (with batteries)	6.8 (without batteries)				15
Max payload [kg]		8	10	7.5	3	4	4	3	12	5	5	2.5	4.5
Operating Temperature [deg C]													
min			-10	-10 (-30 extended)	-10		-20	-20	-20	-20 ?	-10 (-20?)	-5	0
max				50	50		50	50				45	40
Flight time with payloads	empty	5 h 14 min	4 h	5+ h	90 min		70 min	60 min	81 min	150 min	4 h	3+ h (9 l H2)	331 min (20 l H2)
	0.3 kg PL				90 min								
	1 kg PL	5 h 14 min										3.5 h (12 l H2)	
	1.5 kg PL				70 min								
	2 kg PL	4 h 36 min					40 min					150 min (9 l H2)	
	3 kg PL				50 min		27 min					~90 min (5 l H2)	
	4 kg PL			3 h			15 min						
	4.5 kg PL												> 2 h
	5 kg PL	2 h	2 h *	2 h									
	7.5 kg PL			1 h									
10 kg PL		2 h *											
Operating range [km]				177		20	50	40		90	100		80
cruise speed [km/h]			50	35	32		50 (max)	40 (max)	36	36		56 (max)	90
max wind speed [km/h]				35	28		35	30	49			32	50
altitude [m]					300		250	250	4000	4200	4500		
indicative system cost (**)				39 - 75 k€	45 k€		23 k€					38 k€	48 k€

Table 5. Power system & performance metrics for lightweight drones considered in reference missions: blood samples & transport of biological samples

(*) For Quaternium Hybrix 2.1, the maximum flight time with payload is given for maximum payload, but it is not clearly stated for which maximum payload. Both 5 kg and 10 kg were stated as maximum payload.

** (exchange rate 1.2USD/EUR)

Another example of battery-powered drones is Sabrinus 4-20 from Airlift solutions, which is especially designed for medical sample transportation with a large hull (79). The hull has space for insulation that can protect the medical samples from temperature changes, but could also assist in maintaining the battery temperature close to optimum. As the name refers, Sabrinus 4-20 is intended to carry a 4 kg payload for an operating range of 20 km with MTOW of 20 kg. Enough details are not yet available, but with a speed of 40 km/h the 20 km task can be completed in 30 minutes, which based on the above can be considered feasible for this type of drone.

Another battery-powered drone is GUAV8L Ceptor from Globe UAV GmbH, which has operational temperature specified to as low as -20 °C (80). GUAV8L Ceptor has empty weight of 10.6 kg, of which 5.6 kg is the weight of the LiPo battery. The flight time without payload is 70 minutes and operational range on single flight is 50 km. The maximum payload is 4 kg. The flight time with the maximum payload is about 15 minutes. The GUAV4L Aquila is the lighter option from Globe UAV and has MTOW of 9.3 kg (81). The maximum flight time for Aquila is 60 minutes without payload. The maximum payload is 3 kg and the payload can be expected to reduce the flight time in similar portion as with the GUAV8L Ceptor. The greatest advantage of the battery-powered drones is that they are quieter and easy to operate, as the charging can be done anywhere where electricity is available. Down sides are the limited operational time and long charging time, which though can be omitted, if the batteries are easy to replace with new ones.

The best example of the differences between fuel cell-powered drones and battery-powered drones, is to compare the MMC UAV manufactured Hydrone 1550 and Skylle 1550, which are based on the same lightweight carbon fibre frame. The Hydrone 1550 is a hybrid of fuel cells and LiPo battery, first of its kind, and Skylle 1550 is based on LiHV battery (82,83). The both drones have MTOW of 21- 23 kg, but the Hydrone has almost double the endurance of the Skylle: 150 minutes flight time compared 81 minutes. The Skylle has a higher maximum payload of 10 – 12 kg, while for Hydrone it is 5 kg. The endurance and the payloads present the most important difference between the fuel cell and battery-powered systems: the batteries have smaller energy density than the fuel cell system and thus fly shorter, but the batteries can produce higher maximum power for short time and lift heavier loads. The fuel cells are typically combined with a small battery, which provides extra power at peak power demand, and which is charged during low power need.

The Hydrone has been tested to function in high altitudes up to 14 000 feet and managing cold climate in a search and rescue mission in Changbai Mountain in northeastern China (84). The exact lowest temperature during the mission is unfortunately not reported, only it is mentioned that the lowest temperature in the area can reach -30 °C. However, also for the Skylle 1550 the lowest operating temperature of -20 °C and maximum altitude of 4000 m are given. Hydrone 1800 fuel cell drone, a successor of the Hydrone 1550, was introduced in 2017 and has even longer flight time of 4 hours, while the payload capacity remained the same 5 kg as in the previous model (85). The announced lowest operating temperature is -10 °C, although at earlier stage of the development it was announced -20 °C (86). The highest operating altitude is 4500 m.

Fuel cell hybrid drones from other manufacturers to mention are Hycopter from HES Energy Systems and DZ15 from Doosan. The Hycopter is a hexacopter, which has three different size hydrogen cylinder options that are 5, 9 and 12 litres of volume, all pressurized at 350 bar (63). The flight time and the maximum payload depend on the volume of the cylinder, so that with 12 l cylinder the payload can be only about 1 kg, with which the flight time can be almost 3.5 hours. With the 5 l cylinder, the payload can be nearly 3 kg with endurance of about 1.5 hours. The drone has MTOW of 16.5 kg and the operating temperature limit is 5 °C.

Doosan DZ15 is a hydrogen-powered unmanned helicopter, which is capable of carrying 4.5 kg payload when equipped with a 12 l compressed hydrogen tank (87). The MTOW is 20 kg and without payload the maximum flight time is 5 hour 31 minutes with a 20 l hydrogen tank.

If the 20 litre tank weights about the same as a 4.5 payload + 12 litre hydrogen tank, the combination will still reach almost half of the maximum flight time. Doosan declares that the helicopter design makes DZ15 more resistant to wind than the multirotor competitors. The DZ15 can tolerate wind speeds up to 50 km/h (14 m/s), while from the other compared drones the closest are Perimeter 8 and GUAV8L Ceptor with 36 km/h wind tolerance.

The World Record continuous flight time of a fuel cell drone is 12 hours and 7 minutes, which was achieved by South Korean company MetaVista in 2019 (88). They used liquid hydrogen and 800 W Fuel Cell Power Module from Intelligent Energy. The most significant in the record is that only 6 litres of liquid hydrogen was needed, while in the record done with a petrol-hybrid drone 16 litres of petrol were needed to fly over 10 hours.

Flight time vs. payload slopes of six of the presented lightweight drones are shown in Figure 7. The slopes are shown for two drones from each kind of power system. From the discussed drones, it is possible to highlight few options for the user case. If the need of the drone is not continuous and the total distance required to fly during one mission is less than 20 km with the payload, the battery-powered drones are the best choice. For example, G3 Tactical drone, Globe UAV's GUAV8L Ceptor or GUAV4L Aquila can be expected to manage such missions. According to manufacturer, in the Globe UAV's drone batteries can be easily changed during landing in less than 1 minute, which increases the usability significantly. If several batteries are available, new charged ones can be changed to the drone every time it visits the home station. A frequency of 20 – 50 min for the changing the battery is required to keep the battery-powered drone constantly in operation and able to carry its full payload. In urban areas, quiet electric motors in battery-powered and fuel cell-powered drones are an advantage over the ICE-powered drones, which typically have higher noise level.

As can be seen in Figure 7, the petrol-powered drones can clearly carry more payload for longer time than the other options. The fuel cell-powered Doosan DZ15 is however already very close to the petrol-powered systems. The flight time without payload for Perimeter 8 was stated 5+ hours, so the low payload end of the slope is not exact. The battery-powered drones have clearly shorter flight times than the other options. The petrol and fuel cell-powered drones benefit from the option to select the size and thus the weight of the energy storage based on the payload. The battery size of the battery-powered drones are more fixed and the weight of the battery does not decrease together with the energy content.

Figure 7: Payload dependent flight times of six different drones. The petrol engine drones are represented with dashed lines, fuel cell-powered drones with continuous line and the battery-powered drones with dotted lines.

If the range of flight required is longer than 20 km and the drone needs to fly more continuously from place to place without charging possibility, the fuel cell hybrid drones are more suitable. For example, Doosan DZ15 can be flying over 2 hours with 4.5 kg payload and the Hycopter 90 minutes with 3 kg payload. According to Doosan, the flight times of their fuel cell drones with a maximum payload are about 80 % of the flight times without a payload. The flight times of fuel cell drones with payload are thus already catching the petrol hybrid drones in this drone size. Doosan offers hydrogen tanks, which can be easily changed to its UAVs, so the fuelling of the tank does not limit the operational time. The refuelling of the hydrogen cylinders requires a dedicated site preferably outdoors, which is in general not an issue, as the drones anyway require an outdoors site for landing. The refuelling of compressed hydrogen can be done from a storage tank with a booster pump, which adds to the acquisition costs of the drone about 20 kilo euro (k€). With the current track of development, in the future the refuelling can be done also at a hydrogen fuelling station.

In general, the costs of acquiring a drone itself is similar to all the power systems. The best price we got was for the battery-powered drone GUAV8L Ceptor, which was 23 k€. For the other drones, for which the prices were found (Hycopter, Perimeter 8, G3 Tactical Drone and Doosan DZ15), they were between 38 k€ and 48 k€. Accessories, for example parachute required in urban areas, night cameras and transponders come with additional costs and add to the weight.

6.2 Medium sized drones

The application of the medium size drone is to deliver equipment to an offshore oilrig. The required minimum payload capability is 35 kg and the operable range is 80 km. Currently, there are only a few options that could be found for the comparison and they are all running on petrol or kerosene. Three were taken to the comparison, and they are all unmanned helicopters.

The lightest of the three options is a double rotor helicopter Anavia HT-100 with MTOW of 120 kg (89). It has maximum flight time of 4 hours and can carry payloads up to 65 kg, though this includes the fuel. With 35 kg payload, 30 kg is left for the fuel. The fuel consumption of the Anavia HT-100 turboshaft engine is 13 l/h. The maximum flight distance is 400 km without payload, but even with the payload, the required 80 km is reached easily. The Anavia HT-100 can be set up for take-off in 15 minutes and has maximum air speed of 120 km/h. The lowest operating temperature is -25 °C.

The second lightest is the Schiebel CAMCOPTER S-100 with MTOW of 200 kg (33). The empty weight is 110 kg and it has a payload capacity of 50 kg. With 34 kg payload, the flight time is over 6 hours and can be extended to 10 h with additional fuel. The Campcopter S-100 is developed for demanding applications, for instance for military, and comes with its own command centre and radio mast that gives data link range of 200 km. These make the deployment and operating of the system more demanding. The ICE of Camcopter S-100 is designed to run on kerosene designed for military use. The lowest operating temperature reaches down to -40 °C.

The heaviest in the comparison is the UVH-500 from UAVOS which has MTOW of 500 kg and payload capacity of 160 kg including fuel (90). With a 20 kg payload, it has a maximum flight time of 7 hours and still 2 hours with payload of 120 kg. Essentially, it is an ICE-powered helicopter transformed to an UAV. It has a cruising speed of 160 km/h and maximum range of 840 km.

From these three options, the Anavia HT-100 and the Schiebel CAMCOPTER S-100 would fit the best to the user case requirements. The UVH-500 is somewhat over the targeted system

as the empty weight is already 340 kg. The Anavia HT-100 operability is lighter than the CAMCOPTER S-100 and for transportation purposes, the CAMCOPTER S-100 can contain already too many unnecessary costly features.

There are currently no options on the market based on the alternative power systems. With the current battery technology, an UAS able to carry the required payload to the given distance would be very large and heavy to have enough energy stored in the batteries and on the other hand require powerful motors to lift itself.

With fuel cell-powered UAS, the situation is much better. Even though there are currently no ready options on the market in this size, the technology exists and the question is more about finding and assembling the right components. Increasing the system size is advantageous for the fuel cells, as the proportional mass of gas lines and control system decreases compared to the mass of the hydrogen and the fuel cell.

The fuel cell power-to-mass ratio is also higher at larger size systems as can be seen in the Figure 8. The data points on the lines are power-densities of Intelligent Energy fuel cells and the FCvelocity®-9SSL fuel cell series from Ballard. The one separate data point is the power density of fuel cell in the Toyota Mirai (91,92,93). When comparing to the Schiebel CAMCOPTER S-100 internal combustion engine that has a 44 kW power and weight of 23.7 kg, the fuel cell stack of the same power would weight about 25 kg, assuming 1.75 kW/kg power-to-mass ratio based on the Intelligent Energy slope in Figure 8. This assumption is rather pessimistic, as the slope in reality rises faster in the beginning. In combination with the fuel cell, electric motors are needed and for the 44 kW power they would weight 10 – 15 kg. Similarly, the CAMCOPTER engine requires gears for the rotor and the rear rotor, which will add to the weight. Overall, the weights of the two power trains would be very close to each other, thus the biggest difference is the weight of the energy storage.

Figure 8: Power density of fuel cell systems relative to output power. The blue dots connected with dashed line show three fuel cells from Intelligent Energy. The Intelligent Energy fuel cells have optimised power densities as they are targeted for flying. The orange continuous line represents the fuel cells from Ballard targeted for transportation. The power density of fuel cell in the Toyota Mirai is shown in black.

In the CAMCOPTER S-100, the petrol tank is 57 litres, which corresponds to thermal energy content of 507 kWh, and assuming 30 % ICE thermal efficiency is 152 kWh energy for flight operation. We approximate that the mass of the petrol and the container is 51 kg (45.6 kg petrol + 5 kg fuel tank). The hydrogen container of the same mass with currently the best hydrogen container energy density (1.9 kWh/kg) has thermal energy content of 96 kWh. With the 54 % fuel cell system thermal efficiency, the energy for flight operation is 52 kWh, which is a little over one third of what is available with the petrol system.

The flight time of the CAMCOPTER S-100 with 34 kg payload would therefore diminish from the over 6 hours with petrol to approximately 2 hours with the fuel cell power system. Using batteries of the same mass instead of hydrogen or petrol, would provide only 11 kWh operational energy, even though the electric motor system efficiency is almost 90 %. The flight time with the batteries would thus be only about 26 minutes.

6.3 Heavy drones

A theoretical comparison of four different power system technologies is shown in the Table 5 below for a 130 kW power system. In addition to aforementioned power systems, an internal combustion engine running on hydrogen is presented in the table, as this technology represents a possible robust choice for cold climate without using fossil fuels. In the table, most of the numbers are from a table in reference (67), where different power systems were compared for passenger vehicles with a 130 kW power source.

The table is modified to meet the purpose for considering the applicability of the power trains in UAVs. The components for energy recuperation are omitted in the weight calculation, as the recuperation is not feasible in the UAVs. Therefore, also a battery is used instead of super capacitor as a source of electricity for the ICE's appliances and as a mediator and a boost energy source for the fuel cell power train. In the internal combustion engine examples, the weight of the transmission is omitted, as it is not applicable to UAVs.

The MTOW is calculated based on the ratio of MTOW/engine power = 870 kg/ 180 kW of a UAV called Thunderwasp from ACC and assuming linear behaviour (94). For the 130 kW system the MTOW is thus roughly 600 kg. Instead of using the weight of the energy storages with 75 kWh thermal energy as in the reference (67), we also took into account the efficiencies of the different power systems so that all the power system options have 75 kWh of actual energy powering the flight operation. We approximate that the weights of the frame and other components not involved to the power train of an UAV are equal for all the power systems, and have a mass of 100 kg in total. This leaves available payload $m_{AP} = 500$ kg for the UAV power system and the payload. It should be noted that the available payloads calculated here are only theoretical and carrying the maximum payloads with the systems would probably not be practical.

Table 5 shows that fuel cell power train is the closest to the petrol-powered ICE in the payload, having about 78 % of the petrol-powered ICE capacity. The fuel cell power-to-mass ratio on the example is 2 kW/kg, but it is notable that some producers are already producing fuel cells with higher power density of 3 kW/kg (92), which means that the fuel cell stack can already be made lighter. In addition, using the compressed hydrogen container energy density of Toyota Mirai 1.9 kWh/kg, the hydrogen storage weight would be 74 kg and the weight left for payload would be 315 kg. In drones, multiple rotors are often required to rotate at separate speeds, which is easiest to achieve with separate engine for each rotor. In multirotor system, electric motors have advantage over the ICEs, because of their better power-to-mass ratio.

The UAS with ICE running on compressed hydrogen had similar payload capacity as the fuel cell system. The efficiency of the hydrogen ICE is better than ICE running on petrol. However, for the hydrogen ICEs the situation is the same as for the petrol ICE: the actual thermal efficiency is smaller than the theoretical, since the engine is not running all the time at the optimum rotational speed. When multiple engines are used in a UAV, the ICEs are more complex to operate than electric motors. In most applications, it is thus more reasonable to use fuel cells and electric motors to convert the hydrogen into work.

In helicopters, a turboshaft engine running on eg. kerosene is a common solution to produce high power for the main rotor. In turboshaft engine, the combustion of the fuel produces a high temperature flow to spin a turbine connected to the power shaft. Turboshaft engine can be designed to use hydrogen as a fuel to achieve high power hydrogen engine. However, the thermal efficiency of turboshaft engines is considerably lower than for fuel cells, but it increases with output power (95). For instance, Turbotec announces a 35 % electrical efficiency for their 550 kW hydrogen gas turbine generator (96).

Power system	Hydrogen (700 bar) – Fuel cell – Electric motor	Hydrogen (700 bar) – Internal combustion engine	Li-ion polymer battery – Electric motor	Petrol – Internal combustion engine
Total thermal efficiency	54 % [Power train table]	41 % [Power train table]	86 % [Power train table]	35 % [Engines]
Energy storage energy density	1.59 kWh/kg	1.59 kWh/kg	0.25 kWh/kg	12 kWh/kg [H2data]
Weight of 130 kW power system (mPS)	Fuel cells: 65 kg + Air compressor: 10 kg + Electric motor: 26 kg + Hydrogen storage: 87 kg + Battery: 10 kg * = Total: 198 kg	Internal combustion engine: 87 kg + Hydrogen storage: 115 kg + Battery: 4 kg* = Total: 206 kg**	Electric motor: 26 kg + Batteries: 349 kg = Total: 375 kg	Internal combustion engine: 87 kg + Fuel container: 22 kg *** + Battery: 4 kg* = Total: 113 kg**
Capacity left for payload (mAP – mPS)	302 kg	294 kg	125 kg	387 kg

* A battery was used in the mass calculation instead of a supercapacitor in the reference.

** No weight of transmission and energy recuperation was included to calculation unlike in the reference.

*** The weight of the fuel is about 18 kg and a metal container 4 kg.

Table 6. Power systems sized for 130kW power and 75kWh operational energy

6.4 Cold operation

The functioning of the drones in temperatures below zero Celsius is to some extent possible for the battery-powered and fuel cell hybrid drones. For the batteries, the cold temperature affects the battery by slowing down the cell reactions and so diminishes the available

capacity. This can be avoided by heating the batteries, which though also consumes energy and decreases the operational range. Another way to limit the effects of cold is to start the flight with warm batteries. The lowest operable temperature of the battery-powered drones was $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is already good, though sometimes not sufficient in the Nordic countries.

For the fuel cells, the cold temperature is a challenge mainly in the start-up of the cell, as humidity is needed to wet the proton exchange membrane. In cold, the humidity may condense to the cell channels and freeze, blocking the cell. Once the cell is running, it produces enough heat to maintain operational temperature of the cell. From the compared fuel cell hybrid drones the lowest operating temperature given was $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, but it is not clear if the Hydrone 1800 could still be modified to operate at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, as this temperature was announced before the product entered the market.

The cold temperature is a challenge mostly for open cathode fuel cells, which take the oxygen for cathode reaction directly from the outside air. Fuel cell system, which uses closed cathode and liquid cooling, can avoid the freezing issue, as the air entering the cathode preheats in the system. Because more components are required for this type of fuel cell, the weight of the cell is increased. It is thus not worthwhile to build the system on the smallest drones, but already in the medium size drones the proportional weight of the system is not as prominent.

An ICE running on hydrogen would in theory run well in cold temperatures. However, as the fuel cells have better thermal efficiency and they can be modified to run in cold climate, developing the cold running hydrogen ICE would likely be unprofitable. The hydrogen ICE should be very robust and inexpensive to produce to make it competitive.

From drones currently available, the petrol-powered ICE drones are the best option for the cold temperatures. In the cold, the fuel injection to the ICE is the main challenge, which can be overcome with modifications. For example for Perimeter 8 drone, there are already customised systems provided, which make it operable in temperatures down to $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In Schiebel Camcopter S-100 the cold operability is by default even lower: $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

7. Conclusions

The following technical implications have been identified regarding the emerging use of drones in logistics missions in the Nordics:

Atmospheric icing will be a relevant aspect to consider. Flying close to the ground, e.g. at 120m above ground level results in most of the Nordics having icing conditions below 3.6% of the time or 13 days per year. This seems a relatively minor icing challenge, but still may require re-scheduling operations or implementation of an Ice Prevention System (IPS) to allow flight into known icing conditions. Flight at higher altitudes quickly results in larger icing time as it can be observed from Figure 4.

The key operational practice to prevent icing risk in drone operations will continue to be prevention: (i) use of aviation weather information (METAR weather reports) and local weather data during mission planning; (ii) protection of airspeed sensor (97); and (iii) in-situ detection of icing conditions (airspeed sensors, dedicated sensors, monitoring of aircraft performance or handling qualities, etc).

Drones designed for urgent delivery with high availability will eventually have to fly into known icing conditions, and thus will require an IPS. So far, electro-mechanical IPS has been successfully implemented in fixed-wing drones of maximum take-off weight as low as 500kg (Hermes 450). Implementation of electromechanical systems in much smaller wings may be challenging due to size limitations.

Electrothermal IPS with smart delivery of heating power seems also a suitable option for fixed wing aircraft.

Considering fixed wing aircraft architecture, the analysis presented shows that low aspect ratio wings reduce the power requirements for ice prevention systems. Since high aspect ratio is desirable for high aircraft range/endurance, a compromise needs to be reached if an ice prevention system is implemented.

Further, drone configurations of “flying wing” type are well suited for the implementation of IPS because avoids ice accretion in the tail, and results in a simpler and lighter IPS. A low flight speed also reduces heat demand at the leading edge and is also desirable.

In case of helicopter-type drones, the power requirement for an IPS to allow flight into known icing conditions has been estimated as 3%-6% of the engine/generator rated power. In case of the AW139, a medium sized helicopter fitted with Full Ice Protection System, the IPS heating represents 4.7% of the maximum continuous power.

The implementation of an electrothermal IPS in a helicopter type drone such as the Schiebel Camcopter 100 seems feasible, but would have a noticeable impact on mission payload and range.

Besides the pitot – static probes for airspeed measurement, the air systems such as engine air intakes, cooling air intakes should be protected or designed to minimize direct droplet impingement.

In addition to active ice prevention, icephobic coatings seem a good complement to the active IPS. When used in combination, icephobic coatings have the potential of improving the effectiveness of active ice prevention alone. However each combination needs to be studied carefully, for example soft coatings may interfere with the operation of electromechanical ice prevention.

Regarding the aspect of batteries and fuel cells, looking at the currently available options for the lightweight drones, it is clear that for short operations with little payload the battery-powered

drones are a reasonable choice. Their easy operability and availability makes them powerful tool for short range and lightweight applications. For longer operational time than 30 minutes, the fuel cell and petrol-powered drones are the best choices. Between these two, the choice is currently between ecological and cold-abilities. The fuel cells can use hydrogen that is produced with renewable energy sources and petrol-powered drones typically use fossil fuels. Currently, only for the petrol-powered UAS the operational temperature reached $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the other options can operate down to $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. On the other hand, fuel cell and battery powered drones are quieter, which is desirable property for example in urban areas. They also leave very minor thermal trace, which can be important in some applications. For the medium size drones, there are currently only petrol-powered UASs available.

With current track of the development, the fuel cells will be the sustainable choice of the coming years, as the applicability of battery-powered drones is limited by their operational range and time. The electric motors are more applicable in the small drones than the ICEs, and make the drones easy to assemble and operate. The fuel cell-powered drones can exploit the advantages of electric engines, but are not limited by the energy density of batteries.

Some fuel cell UASs can already compete evenly with the flight times of petrol-powered UASs. The fuel cells become even more feasible and can surpass the petrol in flight time, when the materials of the gas containers develop and become lighter. Making the container material half of the current density nearly doubles the energy density of the hydrogen container.

The way to reach the highest energy density for fuel cells is to use liquid hydrogen. The liquid hydrogen allows also packing the hydrogen in the smallest volume. In liquid hydrogen containers, the typical rate of hydrogen loss through boil-off is about 1 % per day. In UASs, this rate is however not a problem, providing that the UAS is fuelled right before take-off. Even higher boil-off rates can be tolerated, as the losses during single operation are negligible. Accepting some hydrogen evaporation from the liquid hydrogen container during operation, allows making the container lightweight and compact, which results to extended energy content and flight time.

The use of fuel cells is optimal starting from about 15 kg MTOW drones in all the sizes up to the heavy drones. At lightweight end, there are already options available, but for medium size and heavier drones, it can be expected to take still few years for ready products to enter the market. Extending the operability in cold temperatures is technically more accessible in medium size and larger drones. Thereafter, miniaturising the cold solutions for smaller drones is the next step.

As the world is withdrawing from the use of fossil fuels, the hydrogen-powered fuel cells offer not only a way to fill the gap left by the petrol-powered ICEs, but they can also extend the operational capabilities of the UAVs. The fuel cells are an integral part of the emerging hydrogen economy.

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